

1 **Disclaimer:** This is an early version of the manuscript from the review process. Te
2 final version of the article is available from Elsevier under
3 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106763>
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5 **Title**

6 Designing an optimal sampling strategy for a national level invasive alien plant
7 assessment: a South African case study
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27 **Keywords**

28 Survey, sampling design, survey costs, validation, monitoring, invasive trees
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Abstract

The availability of accurate spatial distribution data of invasive alien plant (IAP) species is a shortcoming in most programmes and strategies that deal with biological invasions. Such data are required at the relevant spatial and temporal scales to assist decision making ranging from high level policy to local level implementation and the assessment of biological invasion status as part of the monitoring of the range and abundance of invasive species' indicators. Because the complete inventories of IAPs are not feasible due to budget constraints, sampling of a representative proportion is necessary. The selection of an adequate sampling design is critical to ensure cost effective assessments that will also result in accurate and reliable IAP distribution data across extensive and environmental varying landscapes. This paper presents the development of an objective and scientifically accurate monitoring system at a regional level for major invaders for an extensive area such as South Africa by comparing three standard statistical sampling strategies, namely, simple random, systematic and proportionally stratified sampling. The comparison is based on the prediction accuracy of the three designs and their sensitivity to sample size. Sampling was repeated in simulations for each of the sampling designs based on an incremental increase in sampling intensity and compared to an actual field survey result. A generalised linear model was used to predict how accurately the distribution and density of species were reflected by the different sampling designs. Comparisons show that the proportionally stratified design provides the most precise results, followed by systematic and finally random sampling. Further sampling simulations showed that a proportionally stratified design at a national level requires approximately 61 000 sample points to be able to detect IAP species' distribution and distinguish between IAP density levels of five percent and more with a maximum coefficient of variation of 15% at a specified cost threshold of R10 million (600 000 €).

58

59

60 **Introduction**

61 Although the processes and threats associated with invasive alien plant (IAP) species
62 and invasions have been intensively and widely researched (Gilbert & Levine 2013,
63 Ricciardi et al. 2013, Richardson & Ricciardi 2013, Bellard et al. 2016, Paine et al.
64 2016), a gap in the IAP knowledge field are protocols for obtaining accurate spatial
65 distribution data on both distribution extent and abundance (Wilson et al. 2013,
66 Early et al. 2016, Hui & Richardson 2017, Dehnen-Schmutz et al. 2018). Reliable IAP
67 distribution data serves as the basis for a variety of decision-making processes that
68 range from higher-level control policies, strategic planning and determination of
69 management costs to more detailed implementation strategies around prioritization
70 and effective management of IAP species (Wilson et al. 2013). Further to this, the
71 international agreement, namely The Convention on Biological Diversity is aimed at
72 the significant reduction of biodiversity loss and has set out 20 biodiversity-related
73 “Aichi Targets” to achieve the latter (Tittensor et al. 2014). For instance, the objective
74 of “Aichi Target” number 5 is the reduction in the rate of loss off all natural habitats
75 whilst Target 12 deals with the prevention of the extinction of near threatened
76 species. Invasive alien species are recognized as a major threat to biological diversity
77 by the international community under “Aichi Target” number 9 (Tittensor et al.
78 2014). To quantify and monitor progress in achieving these targets, certain
79 measurable key indicators are used (Tittensor et al. 2014). Although there are
80 numerous indicators already in place for the monitoring of a range of environmental
81 variables, the development and implementation of specific indicators to assess and
82 monitor the status of biological invasions at national (Wilson et al. 2018) and
83 international (Latombe et al. 2017) level are in process. At both these scales, the
84 monitoring of the extent and abundance of invasive species have been raised as a
85 critical key indicator to assess and monitor the status of invasions as part of “Aichi

86 Target” number 9. Our work is aimed at the establishment of a scientific accurate
87 and practical implementable monitoring system of major IAP species at a national
88 level that will greatly contribute towards the objective assessment of this key
89 indicator.

90

91 However, surveys to obtain consistent IAP distribution data for ecological diverse
92 areas, such as South Africa (Mittermeier et al. 2011, Driver et al. 2012) that cover
93 extensive areas, in this case 122 million hectares, is a resource intensive exercise and
94 a complete inventory is not feasible (Gitzen et al. 2012, Webster & Lark 2013).

95 Furthermore, a complete census of the entire population will take years to complete,
96 resulting in the population undergoing changes during the inventory period

97 (Gregoire & Valentine 2008, Wildi 2017). This necessitates measurement of a fraction

98 of the total population of interest by means of sampling (Gitzen et al. 2012, Webster

99 & Lark 2013) in an effort to make the assessment more efficient and precise at a

100 lower cost (Raty et al. 2018). The objective of sampling is to infer meaningful and

101 precise estimates of the complete population based on measurements obtained from

102 the sample (Wang et al. 2013).

103

104 The numerous sampling strategies or designs available have evolved over time and

105 reviews of such techniques are found in most statistical texts (e.g. Cochran 1977,

106 Cressie 1991, de Gruijter et al. 2006; Wildi 2017). However, no specific approach is

107 optimal for all populations, survey objectives and data requirements (Gregoire and

108 Valentine 2008, McRoberts et al 2015) and care should be taken to identify the most

109 appropriate sampling design to meet the study objectives (Biswas & Zhang 2018).

110 The error related to inconsistent sampling designs, including the sample size, can

111 result in the survey result not representing the target population accurately (Biswas

112 & Zhang 2018). An effective way of evaluating different sampling designs is by

113 means of sampling simulations (McRoberts et al 2015). For this purpose, objective

114 driven sampling design comparisons have been applied in a variety of fields such as

115 modern forest inventories (e.g. Melville et al. 2016, Raty et al. 2018), vegetation cover
116 surveys (e.g. Mu et al. 2015), soil surveys (e.g. Falk et al. 2011, Thomas et al. 2012,
117 Mulder et al. 2013), carbon stock estimation (e.g. Wheeler et al. 2012, Worsham et al.
118 2012), biomass estimation (Ene et al. 2016) and species distribution or habitat
119 suitability modelling (Hirzel & Guisan 2002, Tassarolo et al. 2014). Final survey
120 results are meaningless without being validated (Radoux & Bogaert 2017), therefore
121 how good or accurate is the survey and the resulting maps (Lewis & Phinn 2011). An
122 accuracy assessment or validation is also vital to allow for quantitative comparisons
123 between different assessment methods, the application of the results in decision
124 making as well as to determine how reliable your long-term monitoring is
125 (Congalton 2001).

126 However, the combination of a large scale survey simulation with a cost estimation
127 and a realistic accuracy assessment strategy has not been attempted for IAPs.

128

129 Objectives

130 Thus, this paper evaluates the performance of different sampling designs by means
131 of repetitive sample simulations applied to an actual IAP dataset, which includes a
132 map of the detailed distribution of 38 IAP species across an extensive and
133 environmentally diverse area. In order to investigate the trade-off between
134 decreased and thus improved sampling variance and available resources such as
135 time and money (Wildi 2017), a cost benefit analysis was conducted whereby survey
136 costs were evaluated in combination with sampling accuracy obtained from the
137 different sampling intensities simulated. This allowed for a realistic total survey cost
138 estimation in relation to sample accuracy.

139

140 This study was done as part of the establishment of a national level protocol for an
141 IAP monitoring system for South Africa whereby research informs management on a

142 cost effective sampling design within a statistically sound, efficient and robust
143 monitoring system (Kotze et al. 2019 for more context). This paper investigates three
144 of the most popular and widely applied sampling approaches, namely (1) simple
145 random sampling, (2) systematic sampling on a regular grid and (3) proportionally
146 stratified sampling (Gregoire & Valentine 2008). The objectives are to (1) select the
147 most effective sampling design, (2) determine a realistic sample size for a national
148 level assessment based on the relationship between actual survey costs and the
149 precision of the estimate obtained within a defined confidence interval, and (3)
150 develop a validation method for the assessment based on independent data.

151

152

153 **Methodology**

154 Study area

155 Sampling procedures should be context dependent and take into account the survey
156 objective (Wang et al. 2013, McRoberts et al 2015), in this case to accurately describe
157 the range and abundance of IAP species. To address the latter, it was important to
158 apply sampling simulations to actual IAP distribution data rather than hypothetical
159 IAP distribution datasets. A fine-scaled field based mapping exercise conducted for
160 the Agulhas Plain in South Africa (Euston-Brown 1999) shows actual IAP species
161 extent and abundance for 38 species at a 1:10 000 scale for an area of 2 160 km² (Fig.
162 1). The Agulhas Plain forms part of the Cape Floristic Region, the most invaded area
163 in South Africa by woody IAP species (Wilson et al 2014). A wide range of
164 interacting environmental variables, including physiological variables such as
165 climate, soil and topography contributes to the occurrence of 16 different vegetation
166 communities or unique types within the area (Mucina & Rutherford 2006). This
167 underlying natural variation subsequently contributes to the diversity of IAP species
168 and results in certain species having a limited and habitat specific distribution to

169 others having a broad and extensive distribution within a large enough area to allow
170 for sampling simulation.

171

172

173

174 **Fig. 1** – Total IAP abundance (percentage) within the Agulhas Plain study area at the
175 southern tip of Africa. Two typical examples of alien tree invasion within the structurally
176 lower growing indigenous Fynbos vegetation on the Agulhas Plain is shown, namely *Acacia*
177 *cyclops* invasion (a) on the coastal flats and a mixed species invasion (b) within a riparian
178 and valley bottom area.

179

180

181 Sampling design simulation

182 Sampling designs were compared in terms of their ability to firstly detect and
183 thereafter to accurately quantify the area occupied by different IAP species. The
184 purpose of the sampling design is to ensure that the sample estimates the
185 predetermined population attribute unbiasedly and with the highest precision
186 (Wildi 2017). Simple random sampling, systematic sampling on a regular grid and
187 proportionally stratified sampling designs were selected because they allow for
188 rigorous statistical inference as well as providing an even spread of sample locations

189 within geographic space (Biswas & Zhang 2018). Whilst simple random sampling
190 and systematic sampling ignore any form of ancillary data to support the sampling
191 design, proportionally stratified sampling makes use of such data to stratify the
192 applicable area to be surveyed. Pre-stratification in the sampling design phase is a
193 widely applied strategy (Raty et al. 2018) whereby the subdivision of a
194 heterogeneous environment into more homogeneous regions can result in more
195 efficient sampling and subsequent inference between strata (Wang et al. 2013). Yet,
196 for such a stratified sampling design to be effective, the strata should ideally be
197 based on environmental variables that correlate with the abundance of IAPs across
198 their distribution range and have a limiting or controlling effect over the occurrence
199 of these species (Lohr 2010, Gitzen et al. 2012, Webster & Lark 2013, Volis 2016). The
200 most meaningful environmental variables selected on the basis of having the highest
201 repetitive correlation with different IAP species across geographic space for South
202 Africa are mean annual precipitation, soil depth, percentage clay content in the B-
203 horizon, and landscape position (Kotze et al. 2019). Mean annual precipitation (Fick
204 & Hijmans 2017), soil depth (Land Type Survey Staff, 1972 – 2006) and clay content
205 in the B-horizon (Land Type Survey Staff, 1972 – 2006) were reclassified into three
206 classes, based on a gradient ranging from low to medium and finally high.
207 Landscape position was obtained from terrain morphological units (Farr et al. 2007)
208 with the lower lying valley bottoms and foot slopes reclassified as one class and the
209 midslopes, scarps and crests reclassified as a higher lying second class. The
210 landscape position classification is based on the strong association between many
211 IAP species and areas of water accumulation and therefore the more moist lower
212 lying areas versus the better drained higher lying areas. The spatial or geographic
213 intersection of these variable classes were done by means of ArcGIS Desktop
214 software (ESRI 2017) and resulted in a total of 54 unique strata or categories per
215 aggregation unit.
216

217 Due to the objective of the study being the determination of the optimal sampling
218 strategy for the monitoring of IAP species at a national level, sample points were
219 firstly applied to the whole of South Africa and thereafter points that intersected
220 with the Agulhas Plain study area were extracted for analysis. Sample point
221 intensity was initially set at 5 000 points and was then increased in additive steps of
222 5 000 up to a maximum of 160 000 points at a national level. Where sample points
223 fell within the ocean or disturbed areas such as towns, they were ignored for further
224 analysis. For the random sampling simulation, points were selected randomly for a
225 given sampling intensity, for example 10 000 points, across the whole of South
226 Africa. This random selection of points at a national level was done without
227 consideration of any form of stratification and thereafter points intersecting with the
228 Agulhas Plain were extracted for analysis. This resulted in a varying number of
229 points allocated to the Agulhas Plain for each random sampling replication,
230 although the national level of points remained the same, in this case 10 000. This way
231 of firstly allocating points at a national level and subsequent extraction and analysis
232 of only those sample points intersecting with the Agulhas Plain ensured that a true
233 random design was achieved for the total area of South Africa whilst the smaller
234 study area remained representative of the larger national level design. For the
235 systematic sampling, points were allocated based on a regular grid representing the
236 corresponding national level intensity of points and also ignoring strata delineation.
237 The starting point defining the grid for each of the different sampling intensities for
238 the systematic design was selected randomly and only those points intersecting with
239 the Agulhas Plain area were extracted for further analyses. The assignment of points
240 in the proportionally stratified design followed a more complex process. The
241 number of points associated with a specific national level sampling intensity was
242 determined for the Agulhas Plain based on the proportional surface area of the
243 Agulhas Plain study area in relationship to the total area of South Africa. Thereafter
244 points were assigned to the unique strata proportionally based on each stratum's

245 area in relation to the total area of the Agulhas Plain study area and subsequently
 246 positioned randomly within a stratum.

247

248 All those IAP species with a proportional extent of more than two percent in
 249 relationship to the total area of the Agulhas Plain were identified to be sampled in
 250 the simulations. This resulted in the selection of ten IAP species that ranged from
 251 habitat specific species with a limited distribution extent of as low as 2.5% to species
 252 with a more general and extensive distribution of as high as 50% (Tab. 1). Sampling
 253 simulations and subsequent analysis of results were done per unique species.

254 Thereafter species were grouped into three classes according to the proportional area
 255 occupied by them. The resulting classes represented a proportional extent of 1 to 5
 256 percent, 5 to 25 percent and finally 25 to 50 percent. The grouping of species with
 257 similar extent (Tab. 1) was done to provide for a better graphical overview when
 258 comparing the effectiveness of the different sampling designs in combination with
 259 sample point intensities to distinguish between different extent classes.

260

261 **Tab. 1.** IAP species selected to serve as response variable in the sampling simulations.

Species	Proportional extent (%)	Extent classes	Average extent (%) per class
<i>Acacia cyclops</i>	50.0		
<i>Acacia saligna</i>	37.6	Medium frequent	40.7
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	34.4	(25-50%)	
<i>Acacia longifolia</i>	21.1		
<i>Leptospermum laevigatum</i>	16.2	Scattered (5-25%)	15.6
<i>Eucalyptus lehmannii</i>	13.0		
<i>Hakea gibbosa</i>	11.9		
<i>Hakea drupacea</i>	3.6		
<i>Eucalyptus cladocalyx</i>	3.2	Very scattered (1-5%)	3.1
<i>Hakea sericea</i>	2.5		

262

263 One hundred sample replications were conducted per unique combination of
 264 individual IAP species, level of sample point intensity and specific sampling design

265 simulated to avoid a potential bias by a rare combination of random numbers used
266 to generate the point locations. The performance of a sampling design is measured
267 as the variance of the sample estimate per unique number of sample points (Wang et
268 al. 2013), in this case coefficient of variance (CV), to enable the comparison of
269 different simulation results. CV was calculated based on the difference between the
270 sample mean and the known population mean and used to compare the different
271 sampling intensities within designs as well as across designs for each of the ten
272 selected IAP species.

273 Generalised linear models (GLMs) were fitted to two levels of data. Firstly, the
274 different sample point intensities were compared with each other within a specific
275 sampling design to determine if an increase in sampling intensity for that particular
276 design and species combination resulted in a significant improvement in reduction
277 of variance. Secondly, the three sample designs were compared with each other per
278 unique species by means of a further analysis of variance to establish if designs
279 differed significantly from each other. The dependent (response) variable being the
280 difference between sample mean and true population mean, whilst the different
281 sample point intensity levels served as the independent (categorical) variable. Post
282 hoc analysis was performed by means of Fisher's Least Significant Difference Test
283 (Williams & Abdi 2010) to determine specific differences. Statistical analysis was
284 conducted by means of Matlab software (MathWorks 2017). The level of significance
285 applied in all analysis was $p < 0.05$.

286
287 Species-specific models of CV development over sample point numbers were fitted
288 with nonlinear regression models in R (R Core Development Team 2019) to show
289 species-specific influence on sampling efficiency. All 30 possible combinations of
290 species (N=10) and sampling design (N=3) were modelled independently. The model
291 used was a nonlinear power function of the form $CV = a \cdot Points^b + c$, where CV is
292 the coefficient of variation, *Points* represent the sampled points in the simulation and
293 *a*, *b* and *c* are regression coefficients. A non-linear least squares algorithm was used

294 to fit the model to the data. Models that did not have a significant c coefficient were
295 refitted with parameters a and b only. Residual standard errors of all species-specific
296 models were calculated.

297

298 For an easier graphical representation data was grouped in three species classes
299 according the three proportional area extent classes (Tab. 1). GLM regression models
300 were fitted to these and average CV was calculated for each unique combination of
301 extent class, sampling design and number of sample points to allow for comparison
302 in performance between sampling designs. The cut-off point for optimum return on
303 assessment resource investment was located where there was no more significant
304 decrease in variance between means, with increasing sample points according to the
305 law of diminishing returns.

306

307 Determining the number of sample points

308 The number of sample points is the largest contributing factor to monitoring costs. A
309 realistic sample size would be based on the relationship between actual survey costs
310 and the required precision of the sample estimate obtained within a defined
311 confidence interval. In other words, it answers the question of how well does a set
312 sampling intensity, therefore fixed number of sample points, estimate a certain level
313 of IAP cover.

314

315 To be able to evaluate different sampling designs and sample point intensities for a
316 specific abundance class, a range of set invasion abundance levels were created for
317 the study area instead of using the varying levels of mapped invasion abundance for
318 the Agulhas Plain. Abundance levels used were the abundance class upper, lower
319 bounds and the class means as defined by the abundance class definitions applied in
320 the current operational IAP mapping standards for South Africa (Working for Water
321 Programme 2003), namely 0.01, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 10, 15, 25, 37.5, 50, 62.5, 75 and 87.5
322 percent respectively. A matrix was created for the study area, whereby each grid cell

323 represented one hectare. A set abundance level was created by randomly selecting
324 the number of cells proportional to the total number of cells according to the specific
325 abundance level to be established. The selected cells were then reclassified as
326 invaded within the complete matrix and thereby provided the different matrices
327 representing each of the 13 set abundance levels to be applied in the simulation.

328

329 Sampling was simulated by randomly selecting the proportion of points for a
330 specific sampling or survey intensity from the different abundance level matrices
331 and repeated 100 times for each unique sampling intensity and set abundance level
332 combination. A wide range of number of sample points, representing different
333 survey intensity percentages, namely 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.05, 0.08, 0.13, 0.21, 0.34, 0.55,
334 0.89, 1.44 and 2.33 percent were applied. The increase in sampling intensity was
335 based on the Fibonacci sequence (Beck & Geoghegan 2010) with 0.01 as the starting
336 point.

337

338 The proportional invaded area obtained from each replication was used to evaluate
339 different sampling intensities in terms of their ability to distinguish between
340 different IAP abundance levels by means of an analysis of variance. The dependent
341 variable was the sample estimate for each of the 100 replications and the sampling
342 intensity class served as categorical variable per unique abundance level. Fisher's
343 Least Significant Difference Test (Williams & Abdi 2010) was used as a post-hoc test
344 to identify specific differences.

345

346 The calculation of survey costs was based on two field survey approaches that made
347 use of vehicle on the road, fixed wing aircraft and helicopter. Travel time between
348 survey points within a topographic varying landscape ranging from areas with
349 gentle slopes to extreme mountainous regions were used in combination with direct
350 survey costs to calculate a final cost per survey point. Direct costs included vehicle
351 or aircraft operational costs, IAP surveyor fees, operational expenses and data

352 capturing equipment. Further to the calculated cost per survey point, accessibility to
353 points within the different topographic environments were used to evaluate the two
354 survey approaches. Four sets of randomly selected survey points were created, two
355 for the Agulhas Plain and two for the nearby Genadendal mountains. The Agulhas
356 Plain study area consists mostly of areas with gentle slopes, whilst it does include
357 high mountainous areas in the southwest, it was deemed necessary to include areas
358 with extreme topography such as the Genadendal mountains to effectively
359 determine survey costs. Each of these areas were surveyed by vehicle, fixed wing
360 aircraft and helicopter. The road survey was further expanded by buffering roads
361 with a set distance within the different survey areas. Survey points were randomly
362 selected within the buffered areas to ensure access to most survey points by road
363 and the road surveys were repeated for these buffered areas. Data captured by the
364 surveyors per survey point were according to the current operational IAP mapping
365 standards for South Africa (Working for Water Programme 2003). These attributes
366 included the total density of IAP species, the three dominant IAP species and their
367 respective densities and size classes as well as the land cover class in which the
368 survey point occurred.

369 Validation of the survey results

370 The objective of the validation is to verify the accuracy and precision of the national
371 level monitoring results. A validation layer is an independent and more intensive
372 sampled area applied to a subset of the national assessment by means of a separate
373 statistically rigorous survey (Olofsson et al 2014). The ten selected IAP species were
374 simulated independently from each other to determine the feasibility to firstly detect
375 a unique species and thereafter accurately estimate the proportional area extent of
376 each species. Secondly, invasions typically occur as non-uniform clumps or patches
377 within indigenous vegetation across a range of spatial scales. The ability of a set
378 sampling intensity to effectively detect and describe invasion abundance across such
379 a varying spatial scale was determined by classifying invaded areas based on their
380 size into three categories, namely small, medium and large sized areas. If all sized

381 invaded areas were to be included within the same stratum, the smaller sized
382 patches would receive far less points and thereby be underrepresented. The invasion
383 abundance class recorded for each invaded area and that consists of seven possible
384 intervals (Fig. 1) was sampled within each of the three area size categories.
385 Repetitive observations across geographic space were created by subdividing the
386 study area into the respective quaternary catchments for the ten IAP species' layers
387 and invaded area size classes with the different density classes as response variable.
388
389 A systematic sampling strategy for the validation layer was evaluated to ensure an
390 even coverage of the total area as well as be independent from any form of
391 predefined stratification. Points for the most intensive grid were 200 metres apart
392 and thereafter the point to point distance was gradually increased with a constant of
393 200 metres for subsequent grids. One hundred replications were done for each of
394 the different sized regular grids with the offset for each grid randomly determined.
395 The proportional area occupied by each species was compared with actual area
396 occupied by that species per quaternary catchment by means of a GLM fitted to each
397 of the ten data sets. Average abundance obtained per area size category for each
398 quaternary catchment was compared with the actual abundance for each category by
399 means of a GLM fitted to the two data sets. The adjusted coefficient of
400 determination (R^2) obtained from each linear regression model was used to evaluate
401 the different sampling intensities across quaternary catchments for the ten IAP
402 species as well as the three area sized categories. The gradual increase in distance
403 between regular grid points was stopped when the average adjusted coefficient of
404 determination reached the R^2 value of 0.2.

405

406

407 **Results**

408 Sampling design simulation

409 The efficiency of a sampling design was assessed by plotting the coefficient of
 410 variation of the sample mean compared to the population mean. The more sample
 411 points applied to an area, the further the variance was reduced and the closer the
 412 sample result matched the population mean (Fig. S1. to Fig. S10.. The variance tends
 413 towards an asymptote, which means that close to the asymptote more sample points
 414 will not significantly increase the accuracy of the IAP inventory. The faster the
 415 variance converges towards the asymptote the more efficient an assessment method
 416 is. The species-specific sampling simulation results suggest that the stratified
 417 proportional sampling design converged faster against the asymptote and reaches
 418 lower variance levels and was thus clearly superior in terms of sampling efficiency.
 419 The only exceptions were noted for *Acacia cyclops*, *Eucalyptus cladocalyx* and *Hakea*
 420 *gibbosa*.

421
 422 It was also evident that there were species-specific differences in the convergence
 423 signified by the coefficients of the species-specific functions (Table 2). As expected,
 424 the extent of the area covered by the IAP species had a strong influence on the
 425 residual standard error of the regressions of the simulated CV as a function of
 426 sample point number (Fig. 2.). This means the models for species with larger area
 427 coverage had been modelled with a higher accuracy.

428
 429 Table 2. Species-specific models illustrate the impact of the extent of individual
 430 species on the residual standard error.

Extent class	Sampling design	Species	Regression coefficients					Residual standard error	
			a	P value: a	b	P value: b	c		P value: c
Very scattered (1-5%)	Simple random	<i>E. cladocalyx</i>	8467	<0.001	-0.5031	<0.001			4.532
		<i>H. drupacea</i>	24190	0.0138	-0.6421	<0.001	5.022	0.0476	2.520
		<i>H. sericea</i>	12600	<0.001	-0.5130	<0.001			2.613
	Systematic	<i>E. cladocalyx</i>	132100	0.0555	-0.8349	<0.001	8.946	<0.001	3.246
		<i>H. drupacea</i>	26870	<0.001	-0.6458	<0.001			2.412
		<i>H. sericea</i>	62820	0.0276	-0.7480	<0.001	5.827	<0.01	2.892
	Stratified proportional	<i>E. cladocalyx</i>	9737	<0.001	-0.5363	<0.001			2.704
		<i>H. drupacea</i>	182900	<0.01	-0.8954	<0.001	5.327	<0.001	1.678
		<i>H. sericea</i>	18740	<0.001	-0.6238	<0.001			1.889
Simple	<i>A. longifolia</i>	917	<0.001	-0.4166	<0.001			0.702	

Scattered (5-25%)	random	<i>L. laevigatum</i>	11400	0.0140	-0.6632	<0.001	2.875	<0.01	0.988	
		<i>E. lehmannii</i>	27390	<0.01	-0.7102	<0.001	2.434	0.0147	1.174	
		<i>H. gibbosa</i>	18810	<0.001	-0.6496	<0.001			1.054	
	Systematic	<i>A. longifolia</i>	9026	<0.001	-0.6507	<0.001			0.847	
		<i>L. laevigatum</i>	753	<0.01	-0.3574	<0.001	5.318	0.0344	0.792	
		<i>E. lehmannii</i>	5554	<0.001	-0.5790	<0.001			1.296	
		<i>H. gibbosa</i>	4020	<0.001	-0.57263	<0.001			1.066	
		Stratified propor- tional	<i>A. longifolia</i>	3678	<0.001	-0.59816	<0.001			0.667
			<i>L. laevigatum</i>	2973	<0.001	-0.54126	<0.001			0.701
	<i>E. lehmannii</i>		8755	<0.01	-0.6669	<0.001	2.794	<0.001	0.693	
		<i>H. gibbosa</i>	15660	<0.01	-0.7030	<0.001	1.254	0.0391	0.713	
	Medium frequent (25-50%)	Simple random	<i>A. cyclops</i>	2399	<0.01	-0.6423	<0.001	1.350	<0.001	0.215
<i>A. saligna</i>			8321	0.0160	-0.6873	<0.001	1.811	<0.01	0.596	
<i>P. pinaster</i>			3377	<0.001	-0.5573	<0.001			0.492	
Systematic		<i>A. cyclops</i>	3348	<0.001	-0.6564	<0.001			0.336	
		<i>A. saligna</i>	574	0.0182	-0.3993	<0.001	2.562	0.0435	0.501	
		<i>P. pinaster</i>	773	<0.01	-0.3798	<0.001	6.128	<0.01	0.705	
Stratified propor- tional		<i>A. cyclops</i>	1872	<0.001	-0.5651	<0.001			0.429	
		<i>A. saligna</i>	1129	0.0107	0.4833	<0.001	1.754	0.0248	0.446	
		<i>P. pinaster</i>	1348	<0.01	-0.4955	<0.001	1.647	0.0163	0.408	

431

432

433

434
 435 Fig. 2: The influence of area extent of the invasive alien species in the study area on
 436 the residual standard error obtained from the simulated CV. The error-plots show
 437 the standard error.

438
 439 For further analysis, the species were grouped in three classes according to their area
 440 extent in the landscape and modelled class-wise (Fig 3). All further results are
 441 reported for the grouped data. From the results it can be concluded that
 442 any of the three sampling designs could detect and quantify all of the 10 different
 443 IAP species sampled. Efficiency of the designs were influenced by a combination of
 444 number of sample points and IAP extent. .More sample points were required to

445 detect IAP species for the very scattered extent class and the CV at the point of no
 446 more decrease in variation was substantially higher as compared to the CV at the
 447 asymptote point for the higher vegetation extent classes (Tab. 3). The random
 448 sampling design was consistently the least efficient design across all three extent
 449 classes, especially for the very scattered class and post hoc analysis showed that
 450 135 000 sample points were required to detect IAP species with an average extent of
 451 3.1 percent (Tab. 1) and obtain a point of no significant differences in CV of 17.7 (Fig.
 452 3 and Tab. 3). The corresponding significant difference limits for the systematic and
 453 stratified proportional designs were 130 000 and 100 000 points respectively (Tab. 3).
 454 The stratified proportional design requires the smallest number of sample points of
 455 the three designs across all three extent classes and is therefore the most efficient
 456 design for such a national level IAP survey.

457
 458
 459

460

461 **Fig. 3** - A comparison of simple random, systematic and proportionally stratified sampling designs.
 462 showing the decrease in the variance (measured as CV) in difference between sample mean and actual
 463 population mean obtained for increasing number of sample points for the three IAP extent classes. The
 464 number of sample points are relevant to the complete area of South Africa. 122 million hectares. Only
 465 CV of less than 50 percent is shown.
 466

467 **Tab 3.** Sample points and corresponding CV at the point of no more significant differences in variance
 468 although there is an increase in number of sample points for the three sampling designs and different
 469 vegetation extent classes.

Sampling design	Very scattered (1-5%)		Scattered (5-25%)		Medium frequent (25-50%)	
	Sample points	CV	Sample points	CV	Sample points	CV
Simple random	135 000	17.7	130 000	7.3	105 000	3.9
Systematic	130 000	13.7	85 000	6.1	75 000	3.5
Proportionally stratified	100 000	17.9	70 000	7.2	55 000	3.8

470

471

472

473 Number of sample points

474 Simulation results were compared based on the ability of different sampling point
 475 intensities to distinguish between different invasion abundance levels (Fig. 4). There
 476 were no significant differences between subsequent invasion abundance levels if the
 477 lowest sampling intensity of 0.01% is used. A 0.02% sample intensity can only
 478 distinguish between a 75% and higher invasion levels. The next level of sampling
 479 intensity showed significant better results because it is able to distinguish between
 480 abundance levels of 15% and 25%. As sampling intensity continues to increase, the
 481 ability to differentiate between abundance classes improves.

482

483 The coefficient of variation (CV) and thus the precision of the estimate also decreases
 484 with either an increase in sampling effort or invasion abundance level or both. Note
 485 the difference in number of sample points required by the different sampling

486 intensities, the associated costs and the expected variance at the lowest level of
487 abundance detected (Tab. 4).

488

489 The determination of field survey costs by conducting actual field surveys allowed
490 for the realistic comparison between field survey approaches. For the vehicle survey
491 it was not possible to reach all survey points in the four study sites with non-
492 buffered roads due to either being refused access to land by property owners or
493 excessive distances of survey points from the road in combination with
494 environmentally inaccessible areas. The buffered road areas provided access to
495 survey points from the road verge and in this scenario it was possible to survey an
496 average of 20 sample points per day by road. The survey rate of the helicopter and
497 fixed wing aircraft were similar to each other in both landscape types (flat area and
498 mountainous). An average of 26 points per hour were sampled and therefore 130
499 points per day if a total of five hours are flown. The combination of direct survey
500 costs with travel time between points resulted in a cost per survey point of R265
501 (about 16 €) if surveyed by road, R218 (about 13 €) by helicopter and R96 (about 5.8
502 €) per point for the fixed wing aircraft. The fixed wing option compared favorably
503 with the more traditional helicopter approach in areas with gentle slopes. Helicopter
504 proved to be the better option for flying in mountainous areas.

505

506 The total field survey costs (Tab. 4) is based on sampling the complete area of South
507 Africa, 122 million hectares, at an average cost of R157 (about 9.5 €) per sample point
508 obtained from the mean empirical field surveys costs for the fixed wing and
509 helicopter approach.

510

511

512

513
 514 **Fig. 4**– Post hoc analysis results showing the lowest point at which a particular sampling intensity
 515 distinguish between a specific invasion abundance level and the preceding abundance level (level of
 516 significance applied was $p < 0.05$). As an example, the lowest invasion levels that a sampling intensity
 517 of 0.05% can distinguish between is a 10% and 5% invasion, but the same sampling intensity cannot
 518 distinguish between a 5% and lower invasion abundance . To be able to distinguish between a 5% and
 519 the preceding abundance level of 3% a sampling intensity of 0.13% or 158 562 sample points are
 520 required.

521

522

523 **Tab. 4** – Coefficient of variation (CV) calculated for each sampling intensity, therefore number of
 524 sample points and the lowest invasion abundance level it can effectively detect as well as the
 525 associated costs of such a field survey (level of significance applied was $p < 0.05$).

Sampling Intensity (%)	Number of sample points	Lowest abundance		
		level (%) detected	CV	Costs (R mil)
2.33	2 841 909	0.5	5.5	437
1.44	1 756 373	0.5	8.0	270
0.89	1 085 536	0.5	9.2	167
0.55	670 837	0.5	12.1	103
0.34	414 700	1	9.7	63
0.21	256 138	1	12.9	39
0.13	158 562	3	11.2	24

0.08	97 577	5	11.0	15
0.05	60 986	5	14.0	10
0.03	36 592	15	11.0	6
0.02	24 395	75	2.9	4
0.01	12 198	100	0	2

526

527

528

529 Validation of survey results

530 The effectiveness of detecting and quantifying invasion decreased with a decrease in
531 total area covered by a unique IAP species and/or the invaded area patch size. This
532 can be ascribed to the fact that species with a small total extent and/or small sized
533 invaded areas or patches were less likely to be intersected by sample points for a
534 given grid spacing compared to larger sized invaded areas. A far less intensive
535 regular grid is required to effectively detect and accurately estimate the distribution
536 of species such as *Acacia cyclops* that covers extensive areas as compared to species
537 such as *Hakea sericea* that has a limited distribution. For instance, a regular grid
538 whereby sample points are spread 3 000 metres apart, accounts for 96% of the
539 variability ($R^2 = 0.96$) of the estimated *Acacia cyclops* population as compared to its
540 actual distribution. Whilst the same intensity grid only explains 50% of the
541 variability of the distribution of *Hakea sericea* which therefore requires a more
542 intensive regular grid to be described effectively (Fig. 5).

543

544 The 1 600 metre grid spacing represents change in the slope of the line of the
545 category comprising the small invaded areas. suggesting that it provides a good
546 compromise between sampling intensity and invaded patch intersection whilst still
547 explaining approximately 74% of the invasion variation (Fig. 6). At this point
548 intensity, approximately 82% and 98% of the invasion variation is explained within
549 the medium and large sized invaded area categories respectively. A 1 600 metre grid
550 spacing describes 83% of the invasion variation for the species with the lowest

551 proportional area cover, namely *Hakea sericea* that covers 2.5% of the study area (Fig.
 552 5).
 553

554
 555 Fig. 5 - Ten IAP species applied as response variable in the regular grid simulation to determine the
 556 independent validation layer. In brackets, the total proportional area covered by each species on the
 557 Agulhas Plain.

558

559 **Fig. 6** - Results of the systematic sampling simulation where distance between sample points ranged
 560 from points being 200 metres apart and to as much as three kilometres between points.

561

562

563

564 **Discussion**

565 Stratification has repeatedly been proven to be an effective method to increase the
 566 precision of estimated population parameters provided that strata ensure a higher
 567 degree of homogeneity of the target population compared to an unstratified
 568 population (Gregoire and Valentine, 2008). In this investigation, the stratified
 569 sampling designs also provided the best results in terms of efficiency. From the three
 570 different sampling designs applied, the proportionally stratified design reflected
 571 invasion of the study area best with the least variation. The regular design
 572 performed second best and being applied in a systematic manner to the complete

573 study area ensures that strata are better represented as compared to the random
574 design.

575

576 To provide an estimate of number of necessary sample points and sample point
577 spacing in the landscape, sampling simulation was further expanded by associating
578 actual survey costs with sampling results (Tab. 4). The simulation results suggest
579 that the lower and more fragmented invasion of IAP species occurs within the
580 landscape the more sample points are required to describe invasion precisely.
581 Quantitative figures on this relation were presented. Actual assessment costs can be
582 reduced by reducing sampling intensity but at the cost of an increased variance,
583 therefore reduced accuracy. It emerged from this study that a five percent invasion
584 or higher can be detected with approximately 61 000 sample points at a survey costs
585 of about R10 million (around 600 000€) for South Africa, comprising of 122 Million
586 hectares. This equates to a sample point density of a point every 2 000 hectares for a
587 national level survey for South Africa at a cost of R157 or approximately 9.5 € per
588 survey point. The average expected CV at a five percent invasion is 15% and
589 improved as the area extent of the species increased. As a result of the costing of the
590 sampling it was opted to conduct the survey by means of a combination of fixed
591 wing aircraft in areas with gentle slopes and helicopter for the mountainous areas. If
592 one vehicle is to be applied in a road survey compared to one aircraft in an aerial
593 survey approach, the vehicle survey would require 3 050 days to survey the
594 approximately 61 000 survey points compared to the 469 days for the aircraft.
595 Assuming that there are 220 working days in a calendar year, the vehicle approach
596 would require 14 years to complete the survey compared to the two years for the
597 aircraft. The total cost for the vehicle based survey would be approximately R16
598 million (960 000 €) without consideration of inflation related increases over time,
599 whilst if a combination of helicopter and fixed wing aircraft was to be used the cost
600 would be approximately R9.6 million (576 000 €). Although South Africa has an
601 extensive road network, it is not dense enough to be able to survey the allocated

602 sample points at a complete study area level. This is due to survey points simply
603 being too far from road sides, located within inaccessible areas or access to land is
604 refused by property owners. Stated differently, if the existing road network was to
605 be used in the national level survey, the complete area of South Africa would have to
606 be redefined as only a buffered area around roads to provide access to survey points
607 and subsequently be able to effectively use inferential statistics to provide a reliable
608 invasion estimation. The road network is also not representative of the full
609 environmental gradient within South Africa and might be biased towards
610 disturbance and other anthropogenic impacts. An aerial survey approach is
611 therefore recommended for such a national level survey due to it not only being
612 more timeously and cost effective but also allows for the total area of South Africa to
613 be surveyed as compared to a buffered road survey. The financial and human
614 resource requirements for the operational deployment of this methodology compare
615 well with three other operational monitoring methodologies in South Africa, namely
616 the national crop estimation system, Western Cape farm mapping and the national
617 land cover mapping.

618

619 The validation method devised, based on actual IAP species distribution data at a
620 detailed 1:10 000 scale, showed clear differences regarding the ability to firstly detect
621 and thereafter estimate individual IAP species' proportional coverage for the study
622 area. Species with a proportional extent of as low as 2.5% could be reliably detected
623 and a regular grid where sample points are spaced 1 800 metres apart can account
624 for more than 80% of the variability of such species. Results for each of the three
625 categories defined by invaded area patch size across quaternary catchments showed
626 an increase in correlation between the results of the simulated sampling and the
627 catchment's invasion as the invaded area patch size increased for the same sampling
628 intensity. The effectiveness for detecting invasion and quantifying IAP densities
629 decreased as the invaded area patch size decreased and varied more strongly for the
630 smaller patches. This can be ascribed to the fact that the smaller the area, the fewer

631 points intersected these patches as compared to the same grid in relationship to
632 larger invaded areas. The 1 600 metre grid was an inflection point for the category
633 consisting of small invaded areas whilst still explaining 74% of the invasion
634 variation within these areas. All the individual species used in the sampling
635 simulations were detected by a 1 600 metre regular grid and 83% of the proportional
636 area cover variation was accounted for in the species with the smallest extent. The
637 regular grid of 1 600 metres is therefore a suitably intensive layer to serve as an
638 independent accuracy assessment layer for the coarser national level proportionally
639 stratified sampling design and could thus be used to acquire validation data sets.
640 Resource constraints limited the accuracy assessment layer to a preselected subset of
641 areas across the total study area.

642

643

644 **Conclusions**

645 The focus of this study has been on selecting an optimal sampling design with the
646 aim of implementing an IAP monitoring system that will provide comparable
647 invasion maps showing extent and density dynamics of IAP species over time.

648

649 Results showed that a proportional stratified sampling provided a more efficient
650 method than regular grid sampling or random sampling. It was shown that the IAP
651 species influenced the accuracy and efficiency of sampling. Classification into area
652 extent classes showed a strong influence of area extent class on the efficiency of
653 sampling, indicating that not the species as such but rather the spatial distribution
654 and extent were driving sampling efficiency and determined the necessary sample
655 point numbers.

656

657 A costing of different vehicles showed that a ground based inventory from a vehicle
658 is not feasible. Fixed wing aircrafts in flat areas and helicopters in mountain areas
659 provided the best efficiencies.

660

661 The result has been the development of a scientifically sound sampling design that is
662 practically executable at a national scale and can be carried out within the confines of
663 the available financial, human and technical resources to enable the assessment and
664 monitoring of the extent and abundance of IAP species as a key indicator.

665

666

667

668 **Acknowledgements**

669 The National Invasive Alien Plant Survey (NIAPS) project is funded by the Working
670 for Water Programme that resides with the Department of Environmental Affairs'
671 Natural Resource Management Programme. This work originated from the NIAPS
672 project and the authors acknowledges the financial contribution made by the
673 Working for Water Programme. Thomas Seifert has received funding from the
674 European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the
675 Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 778322 within the "Care4C" project.

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